

Chemical constituents of *Rhizophora mucronata* of Andaman and Nicobar Islands

Battula Venkateswara Rao*, C. Venkateswara Rao^a, C. Subrahmanyam^a and M. A. Jairaj

Department of Engineering Chemistry, ^aDepartment of Organic Chemistry, Foods, Drugs and Water, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, India

Manuscript received 18 November 2003, accepted 2 September 2004

Chemical investigation of the outer layer of the root bark of *Rhizophora mucronata* Lam of Andaman and Nicobar Islands afforded a rare xanthone, lichixanthone along with atranorin, α -amyrin, β -amyrin, Palmitone, β -sitosterol, dimyristyl ketone and β -sitosterol glycoside.

Two species of *Rhizophora* namely *Rhizophora mucronata* and *Rhizophora apiculata* are common in India¹. Both are abundant in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, the Sundarbans (West Bengal and Bangladesh) and the Tamil Nadu coast. The bark of *Rhizophora* is a rich source of tannin (25 to 40%) and often used in leather industry. The bark is powerful astringent, cures haemorrhage, angina and diabetes¹. Both *R. mucronata* and *R. apiculata* have been chemically examined previously. A survey of literature revealed the isolation of several triterpenoids, sterols and gibberellins from the different parts² of *R. mucronata*. As part of our investigations on marine sources for bioactive compounds we have examined the outer layer of the root bark of *R. mucronata* Lam collected from the Andaman and Nicobar Islands and the results are presented in this paper.

The root bark of plant was collected from the Andaman and Nicobar Islands and identified by Botanical Survey of India, Port Blair. It was air dried (2.2 kg), powdered and exhaustively extracted with n-hexane, acetone and methanol successively.

Hexane extract :

The brown coloured hexane extract (5 L) was concentrated to 200 ml and the dark red coloured solution was kept in a refrigerator for a week. A light cream coloured solid separated out (0.5 g). The solid (mixture I) was separated by the filtration and from the filtrate solvent was removed to get a dark red viscous residue (10 g). This residue showed several spots in TLC; so it was chromatographed on a column of silica gel. This on elution with solvents of increasing polarity afforded four compounds, RM 03 to RM 06.

Mixture I, obtained from the hexane extract, appeared to be a mixture of two compounds (TLC). Hence, it was chromatographed over silica gel when elution with hexane : EtOAc (9 : 1) and (8 : 2) gave RM 01 (0.1 g) and RM 02 (0.05 g), respectively.

RM 01 : Lichixanthone :

It was obtained as pale yellow needles from methanol, m.p. 197–198^o (lit.³ m.p. 192–194^o), C₁₆H₁₄O₅ (M⁺ 286). It exhibited IR peaks at 1650, 1600, 1555, 1450, 1300, 1275 and 1155 cm⁻¹. Its ¹H NMR spectrum (90 MHz, CDCl₃) displayed signals at δ 13.4 (phenolic OH), 6.66 m (2H), 6.32 d, *J* 2.3 Hz (aromatic 1H), 6.30 d, *J* 2.30 Hz (aromatic 1H), 3.89 s (OCH₃), 3.87 s (OCH₃) and 2.84 s (aromatic CH₃). Its ¹³C NMR spectrum (62.9 MHz, CDCl₃) showed signals at δ 182.4 s, 165.8 s, 163.8 s (integrated for 2 C), 159.4 s, 157.0 s, 143.5 s, 115.5 (integrated for 2 C, s and d), 104.2 s, 98.5 s, 96.8 d, 92.1 d, 55.7 q, 55.6 q and 23.4 q. A search in literature showed that the above data of RM 01 were identical with the data reported for lichixanthone (1-hydroxy-3,6-dimethoxy-8-methyl xanthone)^{3,4} and it was identified as lichixanthone, a rare xanthone.

RM 02 : Atranorin :

It was obtained as colourless needles from methanol, m.p. 190–191^o (lit.⁵ m.p. 196–197^o). It showed bands at 1680–1650 br, 1430 br, 1290, 1250–1150 br, 1110 and 1070 cm⁻¹ in its IR spectrum. The ¹H NMR spectrum (250 MHz, CDCl₃) showed the presence of several phenolic groups, aromatic protons, aromatic methoxyl groups and aromatic methyl protons (δ 12.54, 12.48, 11.92, 10.36, 6.51, 6.40, 3.98, 2.68, 2.55 and 2.09). This data is identical with the data reported for the atranorin⁶ and RM 02 is identified as Atranorin.

This is the first report of the isolation of lichixanthone and atranorin, which are lichen metabolites, from a higher plant.

RM 03 : α and β -amyrins :

This is the major constituent of the extract. It was obtained as colourless needles (methanol), m.p. 160–161° and gave a positive Liebermann-Burchard test for triterpenes (pink colour). Its IR band showed a weak band at 3525 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl) indicating it to be a triterpene alcohol. The ¹H NMR spectrum (250 MHz, CDCl₃) showed the H-12 olefinic proton (δ 5.12 t major, 5.18 t minor), the 3 α -axial hydrogen (δ 3.21 m) and many signals due to the tertiary methyl groups between δ 1.25 to 0.79, characteristic of α - and β -amyrins⁷. The mass spectrum showed the molecular ion at *m/z* 426 (C₃₀H₅₀O) and a base peak at *m/z* 218 (retro Diels-Alder fragment of α - and β -amyrins). The ¹³C NMR spectrum showed signals of both α - and β -amyrins⁸, confirming RM 03 was a mixture of α - and β -amyrins and from the intensity of double bond signals (proton and carbon) the ratio of α - and β -amyrins to be @ 40 : 60.

RM 04 : Palmitone :

Elution of column with hexane : EtOAc (9 : 1) afforded colourless solid (150 mg) which was crystallized as colourless prisms (MeOH), m.p. 83° (lit.⁹ m.p. 82–83°). It showed a band at 1705 cm⁻¹ due to a carbonyl group in its IR spectrum. The ¹H NMR (250 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum indicated that RM 04 was a long chain symmetrical aliphatic ketone (δ 2.35 t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 1.63 br, 1.25 s and 0.88 t, *J* 7.7 Hz in ratio 2 : 2 : 12 : 3). From the NMR data and its melting point, RM 04 was identified as palmitone⁹.

RM 05 : β -sitosterol :

Further elution with hexane : EtOAc (8 : 2) afforded a white solid (350 mg), a second major component of the extract, which was crystallized as white needles (CHCl₃ : MeOH), m.p. 131–132° (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 139). It gave a positive Liebermann-Burchard colour test for steroids (pink to green) and analysed for C₂₉H₅₀O (M⁺ 414). Compound RM 05 was identified as β -sitosterol on the basis of comparison of its melting point, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra with those reported for β -sitosterol.

RM 06 : Dimyristyl ketone :

It was eluted with hexane : EtOAc (7 : 3) as a colourless solid (100 mg) and crystallized as colourless prisms, m.p. 61–62° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 58°). It showed a band at 1710 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl group) in its IR spectrum. The ¹H NMR spectrum (250 MHz, CDCl₃) of RM 06 was very similar to that of palmitone indicating that it was also a long chain aliphatic

ketone. It showed signals at δ 2.35 t, *J* 7.50 Hz, 1.63 br, 1.25 s, and 0.88 t, *J* 6.80 Hz in the ratio 2 : 2 : 11 : 3, respectively. On the basis of the ¹H NMR spectrum and its melting point RM 06 was identified as dimyristyl ketone¹¹.

Acetone and methanol extracts :

On TLC examination both the acetone and methanol extracts exhibited a similar pattern hence the two extracts were mixed (15 g each) and dissolved in methanol (250 ml). A 10% solution of neutral lead acetate in methanol (250 ml) was added. The precipitated solid was filtered and the filtrate was saturated with hydrogen sulphide gas. The precipitated lead sulphide was filtered and solvent was removed from the filtrate. A light brown coloured gum (1.5 g) was obtained. This was subjected to column chromatography over a column of silica gel. Elution of the column with hexane : EtOAc (9 : 1) and (7 : 3) afforded β -sitosterol (0.3 g) and RM 07 (0.1 g).

RM 07 : β -sitosterol glycoside :

It was obtained as a colourless solid and crystallized as colourless needles (MeOH), m.p. 290–291° (lit.¹² m.p. 288–290°). It showed a broad band at 3350 cm⁻¹ in its IR spectrum. The ¹H NMR (CD₃OD, 250 MHz) indicated it to be a β -sitosterol glycoside and showed the H-6 olefinic proton at δ 5.34 d (1H), the anomeric H-1¹ sugar proton at δ 4.37 d, *J* 7.93 Hz and six methyl groups between δ 1.03 to 0.7. Some of the other sugar signals were buried under the solvent signal. The mass spectrum showed the highest ion at *m/z* 397 corresponding to the aglycone fragment C₂₉H₄₉. The above data of RM 07 agreed well with data reported for β -sitosterol-3-*O*- β -D-glycopyranoside¹² and hence it was identified as β -sitosterol glycoside.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. R. S. Ward, University of Wales Swansea, U.K. for his help, the Botanical Survey of India, Port Blair, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, for the identification of the plant material, the U.G.C., New Delhi, for COSIST and DRS facilities at A.U., and R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, India for providing some mass spectra.

References

1. Flora of British India, Vol. II, J. D. Hooker, Bishen Singh Mahendra Pal Singh, Dehradun, 1982, p. 436; Dictionary of Economic Plants, J. C. Th. Uphof, Verlag Von J. Cramer, Lehre, 1968, p. 120.
2. S. Misra, A. Choudhury, A. K. Dutta and A. Ghosh, *Phytochemistry*, 1984, **23**, 2823; A. S. Salman, H. S. Imtiaz and M. M. Rabbani, *Fitoterapia*, 1988, **59**, 79; A. Ghosh, S. Misra, A. K. Dutta and A. Choudhury, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 1725; U. Kokpol, W. Chavasiri, V. Chittawong and D. H. Miles, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1990, **53**, 953; E. Saxena and H. S. Garg, *Nat. Prod. Letts.*, 1994, **4**, 149.

Note

3. H. R. El-Seedi, A. C. Hazell and K. B. G. Torsell, *Phytochemistry*, 1994, **35**, 1297.
4. D. A. Okorie, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, **15**, 1799.
5. K. Aghoramurthy and T. R. Seshadri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, **12B**, 73.
6. N. Hamada and T. Ueno, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, **29**, 678.
7. M. J. Kulashreshtha, D. K. Kulashreshtha and R. P. Rastogi, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 1972; P. Pant and R. P. Rastog, *Phytochemistry*, 1979, **18**, 1095; M. C. Das and S. B. Mahato, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 1071; 1997, **44**, 1185.
8. S. Seo, Y. Tomita and K. Tori, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 7.
9. A. C. Chibnall, S. H. Piper, H. A. El-Mangouri, E. F. Williams and A. V. V. Iyengar, *Biochem. J.*, 1937, **31**, 1981.
10. "Handbook of Naturally Occurring Compounds", Vol. II, Terpenes, T. K. Deven and A. I. Scott, Academic Press, New York, 1972, p. 399, entry 4503-003.
11. D. L. Collison and I. Smedley-Maclean, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, **25**, 606.
12. Z. H. Mbwambo, S. K. Lee, E. N. Mshiu, J. M. Pezzuto and A. D. Kinghorn, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1996, **59**, 1051; P. A. Ramaiah, D. Lavie, R. D. Budhiraja, S. Sudhir and K. N. Garg, *Phytochemistry*, 1984, **23**, 143.